

Cemento-Ossifying Fibroma – A Massive Lesion in Mandible-A Case Report

*Sadiya Tarannum, **Pooja Khare, ***G V Ramachandra Reddy, *Swati Surushe, *Shubhi Maheshwari

*Post Graduate Student, **Reader, ***Professor, Department of Oral Medicine & Radiology, People's Dental Academy, People's University, Bhanpur, Bhopal

ABSTRACT

Cemento-ossifying fibroma (COF) is a rare benign fibro-osseous neoplasm commonly involving the jaws. These lesions are predominantly seen in between 2nd to 4th decades of life more commonly in women than men. It's a slow growing mass attain a larger size with passage of time and causes facial deformity if left untreated. We are reporting a case of COF in 50yr old male with huge swelling over a period of 2 years involving the left side of the lower jaw crossing the midline with gross facial deformity.

KEY WORDS: Cementifying, cementosseous, ossifying, fibroma, dysplasia

INTRODUCTION:

The COF is a benign tumor of the oral cavity which is mesenchymal in origin, and it consists of highly cellular, fibrous tissue with varying amounts of osteoid and cementum-like material, that resembles the bone, the cementum, or both, which is most commonly seen in the third and fourth decades of life and is more frequent in women than in men. The periodontal layer contains multipotent cells which are capable of forming cementum, bone, and fibrous tissue^[1]. Radiologically, cemento-ossifying fibroma shows varying patterns depending on the degree of mineralization of the lesion^[2]. It shows unilocular as well as multilocular intraosseous structures. Histologically, these tumors consist of well vascularized fibrocellular tissue with the capacity to produce immature bone trabeculae and cementoid formations, though these findings can also be seen in fibrous dysplasias^[2]. These benign fibro-osseous lesions can involve any part of the facial skeleton, though 70% of the lesions in the head and neck region of which mandible is more common site^[1]. These lesions grow slowly and are unnoticed by the

patient until swelling of the face becomes evident; in a few cases, the tumor may grow rapidly and cause symptoms^[1]. The tumor appears as intrabony slow growing asymptomatic mass causing expansion of cortical plates, displacement of root and facial deformity^[3]. Here we are reporting a similar case of COF with some contrast features which was seen in 50yr old male with gross facial asymmetry.

CASE REPORT:

A 50 year old male patient came with a complaint of slow growing painless swelling in his lower right and left front teeth region since 2 years. With difficulty in mastication and with no signs of difficulty in deglutition or breathing. No underlying significant medical history was elicited.

On extra-oral examination, a diffuse swelling was present on the lower and middle 3rd of the face. Extending from corner of mouth to the 2cm below to lower border of mandible superoinferiorly, and from right parasymphysis region to crossing the midline to left ramus of the mandible mediolaterally. Measuring approximately 6x10cm. With diffuse margins, overlying skin appeared to be normal (Figure 1). On palpation, it was non tender, firm to hard in consistency. Right and left submandibular lymph nodes were enlarged, mobile, soft and non-tender. On intra-oral examination, a massive growth was present extending from right premolar region crossing the

Corresponding Author:

Dr Sadiya Tarannum

Graduate student, Department of

Oral Medicine & Radiology,

People's Dental Academy,

People's University, Bhopal - 462037

Phone No.: 7748812165

E-mail: sadiyashaikh1795@gmail.com

Figure 1: A huge swelling on left lower third of face with facial deformity.

midline up to the left retromolar region. Surface was smooth and lobulated. Mucosa over the growth appears to be erythematous and stretched, measuring approximately 8x5cm antero-posteriorly with gross buccal and labial vestibular obliteration. In posterior region indentations of upper teeth were seen with keratosis and ulcerations. On palpation, it was non tender, firm in consistency, tongue was elevated. With buccal and lingual cortical plate expansion in left side (Figure 2) which was extending up to right side crossing the midline. 41,42,31,32,33,34,35,36,37 were clinically missing, grade III mobility was elicited with

Figure 2: Intra oral examination revealing growth with indentations, keratosis and ulcerations.

Figure 3: OPG showing multi-locular radiolucency with sclerotic border.

38 and 43. The patient was advised orthopantomograph that revealed multilocular radiolucency with sclerotic border extending from left ramus to the mandible crossing the midline upto right second molar region along with the thinning of inferior border of mandible with the root resorption of 43,44,45, 46 and mesial root of 47 and (41,42,31,32,33,34,35,36 and 37) were missing (Figure 3).

Figure 4: PA view of skull showing huge expansile lesion with right angulation of septae.

To know the lower extension of the lesion, since lower border of mandible was not seen clearly in OPG the patient has advised for PA view which revealed multilocular radiolucency with corticated border and expansion of outer cortical plate, thinning and expansion of septae (Figure 4).

Figure 5: CBCT showing single hypodense lesion crossing the midline.

To see the internal structure of the lesion CBCT was advised (Figure 5) which revealed a single large hypodense lesion crossing the midline. The lesion appears to be extending till mesial aspect of mandibular right third molar. The posterior extent of the lesion on the left side is not visible. Superio-inferiorly the lesion appears to be extending from the crest of the residual ridge till the lower border of mandible. Bucco lingual extent of the lesions shows bi-cortical expansion with destruction of the buccal cortical plate. There is displacement of 43 and 44 labially. The lesion has caused inferior displacement of the IAN canal bilaterally. The internal aspect of the lesion shows multiple areas of hyperintensities and multiple incomplete septae in the mandibular right premolar and molar region.

Figure 6: Showing CT scan of face with extension of the growth.

The lesion has caused spike shaped external resorption of the mandibular right premolar and molars. Based on history, clinical findings and radiographic findings a

provisional diagnosis of central giant cell granuloma was given, cement-ossifying fibroma, ameloblastoma, KCOT and myxoma were considered under differential diagnosis. To know the extension of the lesion into the other facial structure computed tomography of face was advised that revealed expansile lesion containing ground glass matrix noted involving the central arch, both horizontal ramus, left lower alveolus and angle of left hemi-mandible. The lesion contain ground glass attenuation with thin internal bony septations and multi focal areas of cortical thinning with subcortical erosion. No other bone or extra osseous soft tissue component seen (Figure 6).

Figure 7: Showing histopathological section with hyperplastic and para-keratotic stratified squamous epithelium.

Core needle biopsy was performed, histopathological examination showed hyperplastic and para-keratotic stratified squamous epithelium with sub-epithelial fibrous tissue comprises fusiform to spindle cells with ovoid nuclei and eosinophilic cytoplasm (Figure 7), it was suggestive of benign fibro-osseous lesion involving the lower jaw. Since the lesion was massive hemi-mandibulectomy was performed from right premolar region up to the left retromolar area with reconstruction free fibula flap. After surgical resection the specimen was sent for histopathological confirmation.

That revealed variable fibroblast and spindle cell proliferation with abundant chunks of immature woven bone arranged in Chinese letter pattern with irregular and round shaped. The immature bony trabeculae, bone lacks osteoblastic rimming and foci of cartilaginous differentiation noted, a final diagnosis made as a cemento-ossifying fibroma.

DISCUSSION:

These benign fibro-osseous lesions can arise from any part of the facial skeleton and skull, with 70%

of cases arising in the head and the neck region and principally seen in the jaws^[1]. It is a slow-growing lesion with prevalence rate seen in women between the third and fourth decades. In which most of the cases are asymptomatic, the growth of the tumor over a period of time may lead to facial deformity, with the appearance of a mass causing discomfort in mastication and speaking or mandibular expansion, and the displacement of dental roots^[2]. Today cemento-ossifying fibroma is widely accepted because both osseous and cemental tissues are seen commonly in a single lesion^[3]. In our case also patient had a large bony hard swelling extending from left molar ramus region crossing the midline of mandible upto right premolar region which was asymptomatic and caused facial deformity, displacement of roots and loss of teeth and expansion of buccal and lingual cortical plates. The highlighting features of this case is seen in male which is predominance is female as compared to male with the ratio of 4:1 mentioned reported by Basudev Mahato et al in 2015^[3] and in an old patient which is mostly seen in 2nd to 4th decader reported by Basudev Mahato et al in 2015^[3] in the mandible crossing the midline.

CONCLUSION:

Cemento ossifying fibroma is a rare benign neoplasm that affects the lower jaws commonly present as a slow growing progressive lesion that might reach enormous site with facial deformity if left untreated. COF should be considered under differential diagnosis for slow growing lesion of the jaws. No classic appearance will distinguish this from other fibro-osseous lesion. It can only be confirmed by histopathological evaluation. Early diagnosis and surgical resection will provide good prognosis and better aesthetic results.

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